

ACT COMMUNITY SURVEY

Questionnaire

Project acronym:	ACT
Project full title:	Communities of PrACTice for Accelerating Gender Equality and Institutional Change in Research and Innovation across Europe
Type of action:	Coordination and Support Action
Duration:	1 st May 2018 – 30 th April 2021 (36 months)
Contract number:	Grant Agreement Number 788204
Programme:	Horizon 2020 – Science with and for Society (SwafS-2017-1)
Date of publication:	January 2019

Contact

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 788204

Welcome to the ACT community survey!

It's great that you decided to ACT NOW and benefit from the ACT project!

ACT is a Horizon 2020 project and short for "[Communities of PrACTice for Accelerating Gender Equality and Institutional Change in Research and Innovation across Europe](#)". The aim of the project is to support research performing and research funding organisations as well as R&D companies in their gender equality actions. This aim will be achieved through creating and supporting Communities of Practice (CoPs) – collaborating groups of practitioners, academics and experts – that work on advancing gender equality on the organisational level and on enhancing the integration of a gender dimension in research and teaching.

The main objectives of this online-survey are:

1. to map actors – practitioners and experts – in the EU-28 who are currently active in advancing gender equality in their organisations/departments and to give you the opportunity to **become part** of the **ACT Communities of Practice** (Part I of the survey);
2. to **get information about the status quo** of gender equality implementation activities in your organisation and your network of collaborators (Part II of the survey);
3. to **identify the expertise and support you would need** to overcome barriers your organisation faces (Part III of the survey) so that ACT can **develop suitable support** and helpful tools to promote and strengthen existing and future collaborations.

You may choose to provide us with your personal data for further contact and collaboration within the ACT project or, if you prefer, to fill in the questionnaire anonymously. You will find our data protection policy on the next page.

Notes on the procedure: *The survey consists of three parts and altogether takes roughly 15-25 minutes to fill in. Please answer as many questions as you can. Answers are saved automatically each time you click on "Next". It is possible to interrupt the survey and re-visit your answers again later by clicking on "Save and continue later" in the bottom of each page. Should you change your mind about answering the survey and want your data deleted you can click on "Leave and delete my data". Once you have reached the last page and do not wish to make further changes to your answers we kindly ask you to click on "Survey completed".*

Thank you for your efforts in helping the ACT project accelerate change in relation to gender equality!

ACTonGender with us! Start the survey by clicking on "Next".

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 788204.

Data protection policy

Declaration on data protection for the collection of personal data

Please read the following information and agree to the processing of your data by ticking the box.

This online-survey is hosted by [JOANNEUM RESEARCH](#) in Graz, Austria. Sensitive data collected through the survey will be treated responsibly and confidentially and will be kept only until the completion of the project (30th April 2021). After this period, the data will be blocked until the applicable expiry period for data storage has elapsed. Anonymised data are analysed by JOANNEUM RESEARCH and the [Jagiellonian University in Krakow](#) and will be available for all [consortium partners of ACT](#). Results of the data analysis are published only in aggregated form, so that there is no direct or indirect (i.e. with the help of further publicly available information) link to you or your organisation.

In the survey, you may voluntarily provide us with your personal data. Contact information you provide will be stored by JOANNEUM RESEARCH and separated from the survey data. The contact details are made available to the following consortium partners exclusively to inform you about ACT in the form you have selected in this online-survey:

[Universitat Oberta de Catalunya \(Spain\)](#), the coordinator of ACT, [Portia \(UK\)](#), [NOTUS \(Spain\)](#), [Advance HE \(formerly Equality Challenge Unit\) \(UK\)](#), [Loughborough University \(UK\)](#), [Technische Universität Berlin \(Germany\)](#), [Karolinska Institutet \(Sweden\)](#), [Science Foundation Ireland \(Ireland\)](#), [Umweltbundesamt \(Germany\)](#), [Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron \(Germany\)](#), [Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique \(France\)](#), [Centre de Regulació Genòmica \(Spain\)](#), [Uniwersytet Jagiellonski \(Poland\)](#), [ZRC SAZU \(Slovenia\)](#), and [Haskoli Islands \(Iceland\)](#).

JOANNEUM RESEARCH provides the consortium partners with the personal contact data and anonymous survey data separately, they will not be able to link the two data sets.

Do you agree to the processing of your data?

I hereby declare my consent to the processing of the collected data in the above-mentioned scope

Your consent can be revoked at any time with effect for the future by sending an e-mail to act@joanneum.at. Further information can be found in our [Privacy Policy](#) and in the ACT [Information Sheet and Consent Form](#) for this online-survey as well as on the [ACT website](#).

Part I: General Information & Expression of Interest

Please indicate the **official name of the organisation you currently work for**.

This information is used to match all surveys that we may receive from the same organisation. Should you be affiliated with more than one organisation we kindly ask to fill in the survey for the one you are mainly affiliated with and for which you will fill out this survey.

Important note: Once you start typing, organisations will be suggested as listed in our database. Please try to find your organisation in the list first before typing it yourself. If you cannot find your organisation in the system please provide the official name (in English) as it can be found on the website. Please avoid accents or special characters.

Organisation:

Please indicate if the organisation you work for has only one location or several.

- The organisation has only one location
- The organisation has several locations in the same country
- The organisation has several locations in different countries (international organisation)

Please enter the official website of your organisation.

Website:

In which country is your organisation located?

Should you work at an international organisation please indicate the country of the headquarters of your organisation.

EU-28:

Other:

Please enter the city name and postal code of the organisation (headquarters).

Important note: This information will be used to visualise collaboration between institutions around the topic of gender equality on a geographical map. City names are suggested once you start typing. If you can't find your city please try the English name.

City:

Postal Code:

Please indicate the type of your organisation.

- Public higher education institution
- Private higher education institution
- Publicly funded research institution
- Private research institution
- Scientific or institutional network
- Research Funding Organisation
- Non-for-profit organisation, charity, non-governmental organisation, foundation or similar
- Private R&D Company
- Other type: ⇒ EI18_01 ⇐ (please specify)

In which scientific area(s) does your organisation conduct or fund research and/or educational activities?

Please indicate all scientific areas applicable to your organisation.

- Natural Sciences
- Engineering and Technology
- Medical and Health Sciences
- Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences
- Social Sciences
- Humanities and the Arts
- All of the above
- None of the above

Please indicate if you answer the survey for the whole organisation or on the level of a single department/faculty.

Note that all of the following questions (unless otherwise indicated) shall be answered with respect to the selected level. This includes the implementation of gender equality measures, any related collaboration activities as well as barriers and needs. Please select the level in which you feel more comfortable to answer these questions.

- The whole organisation
- Level of department/faculty

What is your current position in the ⇒ EI10 ⇐?

Multiple answers possible.

- Management/leadership position
- Human Resource Manager/Human Resource Specialist
- Women's representative/Equal Opportunities Officer/Diversity Officer or similar
- Academic teacher/researcher/scientific personnel
- Other position: ⇒ EI18_02 ⇐ (please specify)

Please indicate the way in which your work addresses gender equality issues.

Multiple answers possible.

- My work is directly related to gender equality implementation in my organisation/department e.g. as HR Manager, Equal Opportunities Officer, minorities representative, working in a project on gender equality etc.
 - I am a leader/manager of an organisation/department involved in activities related to gender equality
 - I am involved in institutional efforts for gender equality implementation as an individual researcher/employee
 - I integrate a gender dimension into research and/or teaching as an individual effort
 - I advise other organisations regarding gender equality
-
- My work does not address gender equality in any way

text('No GE work')

Remark

Because your work does not address gender equality in any way we kindly ask you to **forward the invitation/link to this online-survey** to someone you know inside your organisation that is concerned with gender equality work (either promoting gender equality within the organisation or integrating a gender dimension in research or teaching). Here is the link to the survey:
<https://fragebogen.joanneum.at/ACT/>

Thank you so much for your cooperation and support!

If you are nonetheless interested in the rest of the online-survey you may continue by clicking on **"Next"**. Otherwise you can leave the survey by closing the browser window.

question('EI14')

Are there individuals in your ⇒ EI10 ⇐ who are officially responsible for implementing gender equality on the organisational level?

 Yes No

text('Forward')

Remark

If yes, we kindly ask you to **forward the invitation/link to the online-survey** to the respective person(s). Here is the link to the survey: <https://fragebogen.joanneum.at/ACT/>

Thank you for your help!

To which extent would you like to be involved in the [ACT project](#)?

Multiple answers possible.

- I would like to receive regular information about the project through the newsletter
- I am interested in participating in ACT events (including conferences and workshops)
- I am interested in becoming part of a Community of Practice
- I am interested in being part of the ACT community by being listed as contact person for my institution on the ACT website

- I am not interested in being involved in ACT

About ACT

ACT is a Horizon 2020 project that seeks to advance gender equality at European Research Performing (RPO) and Research Funding Organisations (RFO). To achieve this goal, ACT aims at facilitating the collaboration between experienced and less experienced institutions when it comes to implementing gender equality measures and including a gender dimension in research and teaching.

The ACT project will set up and support an international network of Communities of Practice (CoPs) as agents to develop gender equality actions at research organisations in the European Research Area. For this purpose, ACT will establish the first European network of Communities of Practice by supporting 7 new or consolidated CoPs working on gender equality in R&I, assess their needs, and offer opportunities to foster synergies and innovation in this field.

question('EI16', 'spacing=0')

To be contacted by ACT according to your expression of interest to be involved in the project (as selected on the previous page) please provide your contact details below.

Please select your city/country among the suggested options (will appear once you start typing). For our data protection policy with respect to the collection of personal data within the ACT project see the information and links provided below.

Surname:

First name:

Email:

Postal Code:

question('EI22', 'spacing=0')

City:

question('EI23', 'spacing=0')

Country:

question('EI17')

Gender (optional): [Please choose]

Note on data protection:

Your contact information will be stored by JOANNEUM RESEARCH and used exclusively by the ACT consortium members according to your expression of interest to be involved in the project (selection on the previous page). Your personal data will **not** be linked to the answers you provide in this survey. Further information can be found in the ACT [Information Sheet and Consent Form](#). Your consent can be revoked at any time with effect for the future by sending an e-mail to act@joanneum.at.

question('DP04', 'spacing=10')

Please agree to the use of your contact data by the ACT consortium members:

I hereby agree that my contact information will be used to be contacted by ACT.

question('DP05')

Please agree that your contact data will be shown on the ACT website:

I hereby agree that my name, my email-address and name of organisation I am affiliated with will be published on the ACT-website so that people can contact me for network activities on gender equality.

Part II: Gender Equality in the Organisation & Related Network Activities

You have now reached the 2nd part of the survey!

In this part we would like to ask you about the status quo of gender equality implementation activities in your ⇒ EI10 ⇐ and your network of collaborators. This information will be analysed to provide an overall picture on gender equality activities in European research performing and research funding organisations and will **not be linked** in any way to the personal data you provided in the first section.

Does your ⇒ EI10 ⇐ have a Gender Equality Plan (GEP) or equivalent document/policy (e.g. a Diversity Plan including gender or a relevant strategy)?

- Yes, there is a GEP or equivalent on the organisational level
- Yes, there is a GEP or equivalent on the department level
- No, but we are working on developing a GEP
- No, we used to have one, but it is no longer in place
- No GEP planned or in place

I don't know

question('GS03')

Which steps have you already undertaken on the way to implementing a GEP or equivalent document/policy?

Multiple answers possible.

- Status quo assessment of gender in/equality
- Informal/formal talks with management
- Informal/formal talks with other stakeholders
- Setting up an informal/formal committee
- Discussing the needs of the institution/employees in terms of gender equality
- Draft of GEP or equivalent document
- Enacting of a GEP in process
- Other steps: ⇒ GS18_01 ⇐ (please specify)

question('GS73', 'combine=GS74')

Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) can focus on different fields of action. Please indicate which of the following measures are included in the GEP of your ⇒ EI10 ⇐ and rate their effectiveness.

Multiple answers possible. If you are still developing your GEP and therefore cannot assess the effectiveness yet please select "I can't assess this".

	not effective	rather not effective	rather effective	very effective	I can't assess this
<input type="checkbox"/> Gender equality office, diversity office, gender equality committee or similar	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Commitment to gender mainstreaming	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Implementation of gender budgeting	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Collection of sex-/gender-disaggregated data	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Enhancing women's recruitment	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Equal pay measures	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Enhancing women's promotion	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Promoting equal representation in decision making	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Flexible career trajectory schemes	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Flexible working arrangements	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Child care support	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Enhancing women's visibility	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Support for dual career couples	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Awareness raising measures	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Measures addressing non-discrimination and gender diversity	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Measures combating sexual harassment	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Measures addressing the integration of a gender dimension into research	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Measures addressing the integration of a gender dimension in curricula and teaching material	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Other measures: ⇒ GS18_02 ⇐	<input type="radio"/>				

question('GS75', 'combine=GS76')

Are there any additional measures concerning gender equality that exist in your ⇒ EI10 ⇐, which are not included in the GEP?

Multiple answers possible. Please indicate also your opinion on the **effectiveness** of the respective measures **within your** ⇒ EI10 ⇐.

	not effective	rather not effective	rather effective	very effective	I can't assess this
<input type="checkbox"/> Gender equality office, diversity office, gender equality committee or similar	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Commitment to gender mainstreaming i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Implementation of gender budgeting i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Collection of sex-/gender-disaggregated data	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Enhancing women's recruitment i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Equal pay measures	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Enhancing women's promotion i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Promoting equal representation in decision making i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Flexible career trajectory schemes i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Flexible working arrangements i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Child care support i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Enhancing women's visibility i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Support for dual career couples i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Awareness raising measures i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Measures addressing non-discrimination and gender diversity	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Measures combating sexual harassment	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Measures addressing the integration of a gender dimension into research i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Measures addressing the integration of a gender dimension in curricula and teaching material	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Other measures: ⇒ GS18_03 ⇐	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> No additional measures					
<input type="checkbox"/> Not specified yet					

question('GS06')

Does your ⇒ EI10 ⇌ undertake any action or have any measures to address gender equality on the organisational level?

- Yes
- No, but we are developing such measures
- No, and we are not planning to develop any

I don't know

question('GS77','combine=GS78')

Which measures are in use to address gender equality issues in the ⇒ EI10 ⇐?

Multiple answers possible. Please indicate also your opinion on the **effectiveness** of the respective measures **within your** ⇒ EI10 ⇐.

	not effective	rather not effective	rather effective	very effective	I can't assess this
<input type="checkbox"/> Gender equality office, diversity office, gender equality committee or similar	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Commitment to gender mainstreaming i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Implementation of gender budgeting i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Collection of sex-/gender-disaggregated data	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Enhancing women's recruitment i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Equal pay measures	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Enhancing women's promotion i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Promoting equal representation in decision making i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Flexible career trajectory schemes i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Flexible working arrangements i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Child care support i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Enhancing women's visibility i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Support for dual career couples i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Awareness raising measures i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Measures addressing non-discrimination and gender diversity	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Measures combating sexual harassment	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Measures addressing the integration of a gender dimension into research i	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Measures addressing the integration of a gender dimension in curricula and teaching material	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="checkbox"/> Other measures: ⇒ GS18_04 ⇐	<input type="radio"/>				

Do you see the need for introducing a Gender Equality Plan (GEP) in your ⇒ EI10 ⇐?

Yes

No

Why/why not?

Please explain your answer briefly (not more than 500 characters).

Which of the following activities are implemented by your ⇒ EI10 ⇐ when it comes to including a gender dimension in research and teaching ⓘ?

Multiple answers possible. Please select all activities that were implemented in at least one case (i.e. activities do not necessarily have to apply for all conducted projects, courses etc.).

Integration of a sex/gender dimension in research programmes and policies (e.g. funding or implementation of gender-sensitive research)

Collection of sex-/gender-disaggregated data within research projects

Inclusion of sex/gender issues in teaching curricula

Dedicated gender issues diploma/gender studies programme

Training for research staff regarding methods for implementing gender as a research dimension

Use of sex/gender criteria in the evaluation of the research content of programmes, projects and studies

Dedicated budget for gender-related projects and/or studies

Dedicated office/qualified staff advising on the inclusion of a gender dimension in research and/or teaching

Guidelines and/or training materials for researchers and research managers on integrating sex/gender aspects in the research content of programmes, projects and/or studies

Special research unit to conduct research projects that consider a gender dimension

Inclusion of a gender dimension in research monitoring and evaluation tools/systems

Other activities: ⇒ GS18_05 ⇐ (please specify)

None of the above

With how many organisations has your ⇒ EI10 ⇐ cooperated in the last 3 years to promote gender equality on the organisational level and/or to integrate a gender dimension into research and teaching?

0

1-3

4-6

7-10

11-20

21-50

More than 50

question('GS16')

Is/was your ⇒ EI10 ⇌ part of any project listed below or any other projects funded by the Seventh Framework Program (FP7) and/or Horizon 2020 for implementing gender equality?

Multiple answers possible.

- Baltic Gender
- CHANGE
- EGERA
- EQUALT-IST
- FESTA
- GARCIA
- GEECCO
- GENDERTIME
- GENERA
- GENIS LAB
- GENOVATE
- INTEGER
- LIBRA
- PLOTINA
- R-I PEERS
- SAGE
- STAGES
- SUPERA
- TARGET
- TRIGGER
- Other project(s): ⇒ GS18_18 ⇌ (please specify)

None of the above

⇒ **GS16** ⇒ **have been your** ⇒ **EI10** ⇒ **'s main external cooperation partners for implementing gender equality within the last 3 years?**

Important note: You may list up to 5 partners. Please indicate also the country and city for each partner. This information will be used to anonymously visualise cooperations on a geographic map. Options are suggested once you start typing. Please try to find the respective organisation/country/city among the suggested options before typing it yourself (you may need to type the information in English). When listing an organisation **not** available in our database, please indicate the **official name in English** and avoid accents or special characters.

Partner 1:

Country:

City:

Partner 2:

Country:

City:

Partner 3:

Country:

City:

Partner 4:

Country:

City:

Partner 5:

Country:

City:

question('GS37')

No additional cooperation partners for implementing gender equality

We kindly ask you to forward the invitation/link to this survey to your respective partners!

Here is the link: <https://fragebogen.joanneum.at/ACT>

In which way did your ⇒ EI10 ⇐ cooperate with external partners to improve gender equality on the organisational level within the last 3 years?

Multiple answers possible.

- Cooperation in at least one project to implement gender equality measures
- Cooperation in an international/national network/association, in which gender equality is a main focus
- Cooperation in an international/national network/association, in which gender equality is of secondary focus
- Exchange of gender expertise (know-how, tool kits, personnel, etc.)
- Joint workshops/trainings on gender equality
- Use of shared resources (e.g. company kindergarten, databases)
- Learning about gender equality through reflection and dialogue
- Formulation of common objectives and specific action plan
- Commitment to a shared vision
- Other way(s): ⇒ GS18_11 ⇐ (please specify)

No cooperation for integrating gender equality on the organisational level

In which way did your ⇒ EI10 ⇐ cooperate with external partners when it comes to integrating a gender dimension into research and teaching within the last 3 years?

Multiple answers possible.

- Cooperation in at least one research project that integrated the analytical dimension on gender
- Cooperation in an international/national network/association, in which integration of gender into research and teaching is a main focus
- Exchange of gender expertise in specific disciplines (know-how, tool kits, personnel, etc.)
- Joint workshops/trainings on integrating gender into research and teaching
- Joint publications
- Exchange of research ideas/transmission of research needs
- Strategic partnership with formulation of common objectives and an action plan
- Establishment of a legal organisation (research association, joint venture, Research Corporation, civil partnership, cooperation agreement, etc.)
- Commitment to a shared vision
- Other way(s): ⇒ GS18_17 ⇐ (please specify)

No cooperation for integrating a gender dimension in research and teaching

How does your ⇒ EI10 ⇐ benefit from the participation in networks or shared projects in which it is or was actively engaged in?

Multiple answers possible.

- Information exchange in relation to news, conferences, available funding etc.
- Knowledge exchange: good practice exchange, toolkits
- Expertise provision through lectures, trainings, counselling, mentorship, job shadowing etc.
- Possibility of external evaluation, peer evaluation
- Networking, gathering contacts for future actions
- Organising common events
- Granting awards, certificates, prizes
- Providing financial resources
- Other benefit(s): ⇒ GS18_19 ⇐ (please specify)

Part III: Gender Equality Successes, Needs & Support**You have now reached the 3rd and final part of the survey!**

The last part will gather your opinions and feelings about gender equality implementation processes within your ⇒ EI10 ⇐. We would like to learn about the barriers your ⇒ EI10 ⇐ faces in the implementation of gender equality and about the expertise and support you would need in those challenges so that ACT can develop suitable support.

In your opinion, have you observed progress in your ⇒ EI10 ⇐ when it comes to gender equality issues in the last 3 years?

- Yes, there is progress
- No, there is no progress
- No, gender equality issues have been regressing

-
- I can't assess this

In your opinion, which of the following barriers affect the implementation of gender equality in your ⇒ EI10 ⇐?

Multiple answers possible.

- Lack of commitment/support from organisation management
- Active resistance from organisation management
- Lack of commitment/support from employees/staff members
- Active resistance from employees/staff members
- Responsibilities for action are not assigned clearly
- Lack of coordination
- Lack of necessary data (statistical, administrative) on the issue
- Lack of expertise within the organisation/department
- Regulations or policies (e.g. labour law) at national or regional level are not specifically supportive for gender equality implementation
- Lack of financial resources
- Lack of personnel/time
- Lack of accountability/monitoring
- Other barrier(s): ⇒ GN09_02 ⇐ (please specify)

No barriers so far

I can't assess this

What kind of internal factors would be needed to improve gender equality in your ⇒ EI10 ⇐?

Multiple answers possible.

- Gender know-how/expertise
- Strategies/arguments to overcome resistances
- Financial resources
- Better coordination of actions e.g. through establishing a gender equality office
- Better access to data (statistical, administrative) on the issue
- More support from organisation management
- More support from other stakeholders
- Participation in a network/project on gender equality (or Community of Practices)
- Special incentives (certificates, awards, etc.)
- Regular monitoring of gender equality status quo
- Clear responsibility for implementation
- Other factor(s): ⇒ GN09_04 ⇐ (please specify)

I can't assess this

In the last 3 years, has your ⇒ EI10 ⇐ received any of the following forms of external support for gender equality implementation?

Multiple answers possible.

- External trainings (e.g. on unconscious bias, discrimination, ...)
- Base for action through a firm legal basis and regulations
- Expertise in form of talks, lectures, counselling
- External evaluation of existing GEP/gender equality measures
- Funding from international grants
- Funding from national grants
- Funding from other sources than grants
- Other public policy measures: ⇒ GN09_05 ⇐ (please specify)
- Other external support: ⇒ GN09_06 ⇐ (please specify)

No external support so far

I don't know

In your opinion, what kind of external support would be needed to improve gender equality in your ⇒ EI10 ⇐?

Multiple answers possible.

- External trainings (e.g. on unconscious bias, discrimination, ...)
- Base for action through a firm legal basis and regulations
- Expertise in form of talks, lectures, counselling
- External evaluation of existing GEP/gender equality measures
- Funding from international grants
- Funding from national grants
- Funding from other sources than grants
- Other public policy measures: ⇒ GN09_07 ⇐ (please specify)
- Other external support: ⇒ GN09_08 ⇐ (please specify)

No external support needed

I can't assess this

Is there anything you would like to add?

Feel free to leave any additional comments or remarks about gender equality issues, the ACT project and/or this online-survey. Please limit your answer to 500 characters.

You have now reached the last page of the survey!

Your answers have been saved. If you wish to make any changes to your answers, you can go back to the respective questions by clicking on **"Back"**. If you would like to revise your answers later, you can click on **"Save and continue later"**. You will then receive a personal link with which you can re-access your survey and continue where you left off.

Otherwise, please exit the survey by clicking on **"Survey completed"**, but note that no more changes can be made after that. Once you are finished we kindly ask you to **forward the invitation/link to this survey** to your collaboration partners and others who may be interested in promoting gender equality. Here is the link to the survey: **<https://fragebogen.joanneum.at/ACT/>**

Thank you for your cooperation!

Thank you for completing the survey!

ACT will contact you according to your expression of interest to be involved in the project.

You may now close the browser window.

Should you have any questions regarding ACT or this survey please contact us: act@joanneum.at